

The Unjournal

Evaluation Summary and Metrics: “The Returns to Science In the Presence of Technological Risks”, Unjournal applied Stream

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ABSTRACT

We organized three evaluations of the paper: “The Returns to Science In the Presence of Technological Risks”^[1]. To read these evaluations, please see the link below. The author has responded in detail, also linked below.

Note: Applied and Policy Stream

This paper was evaluated as part of our “applied and policy stream”, described [here](#). The ratings should not be directly compared to those in our main academic stream.

Evaluations

1. [Mike Hinge](#)
2. [Yassin Alaya](#)
3. [Gregory Lewis](#)

Author response

[Matt Clancy’s response](#)

Overall ratings

We asked evaluators to provide overall assessments as well as ratings for a range of specific criteria.

I. Overall assessment (See footnote¹)

II. Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5): On a ‘scale of journals’, what ‘quality of journal’ should this be published in?² *Note: 0= lowest/none, 5= highest/best.*

	Overall assessment (0-100)	Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5)
Mike Hinge	80	N/A
Yassin Alaya	N/A	4.5
Gregory Lewis	71	N/A

See “[Metrics](#)” below for a more detailed breakdown of the evaluators’ ratings across several categories. To see these ratings in the context of all Unjournal ratings, with some analysis, see our [data presentation here](#).³

See [here](#) for the current full evaluator guidelines, including further explanation of the requested ratings.

Evaluation summaries

Mike Hinge

- The paper as a whole is a high quality assessment of the likely trade-offs of scientific progress versus biorisks.
- It makes good use of an empirical base, and different methods. It shows model sensitivities and allows assumptions to be changed.
- It does not definitely answer if accelerating science is good, primarily due to uncertainties around existential risks.
- Its conclusions are sensitive to the discount factor and more work would be needed before considering actions at a larger scale.

Yassin Alaya

The Returns To Science In The Presence Of Technological Risks' by Matt Clancy considers whether the benefits of science outweigh its risks by modelling the welfare effects of globally pausing science for one year. The benefits considered are increases in per capita income and a decreasing mortality rate. The risks are advances in biotechnology which might enable malicious actors to create dangerous pathogens. These risks are modelled as an increased rate of mortality due to more frequent, more severe pandemics and as a risk of extinction due to a pandemic killing the entire human population.

In a model without extinction risk, the benefits of science strongly outweigh the risks. It thus seems that the qualitative result[s] when ignoring the possibility of science increasing extinction risk are not sensitive to parameter choices. When extinction risk is accounted for, the conclusions depend on how valuable one reckons the possible future of humanity (which would be lost due to extinction) to be.

Gregory Lewis

I was principally tasked with kicking the tires on the 'biocatastrophe' parameters as this is my subject of expertise. They check out, and I can find little to criticise.

Either I'm missing something, or the paper seems to be making a large mistake by comparing 'all of the benefits' of science on the one hand versus 'only the technical risks of biocatastrophe' on the other. Is AI risk the elephant in the room?

Metrics

Ratings

[See here](#) for details on the categories below, and the guidance given to evaluators.

	Evaluator 1: Mike Hinge		Evaluator 2: Yassin Alaya		Evaluator 3: Gregory Lewis		
Rating category	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*	Comments
Overall assessment ⁴	80	(60, 88)	N/A	N/A	71	(27, 87)	
Claims, strength, characterization of evidence ⁵	85	(70, 90)	N/A	N/A	79	(16, 90)	
Advancing knowledge and practice ⁶	75	(65, 85)	65	(30, 100)	81	(56, 96)	
Methods: Justification, reasonableness, validity, robustness ⁷	75	(65, 85)	60	(45, 75)	75	(88, 33)	8
Logic & communication ⁹	85	(70, 90)	50	(30, 70)	88	(64, 95)	10
Open, collaborative, replicable ¹¹	90	(80, 95)	60	(35, 85)	89	(76, 99)	
Real-world relevance 12 , 13	75	(65, 83)	70	(50, 90)	65	(18, 89)	14

Relevance to global priorities ¹⁵ , 16	75	(65, 83)	90	(80, 100)	60	(40, 75)	
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Journal ranking tiers

[See here](#) for more details on these tiers.

	Evaluator 2 Yassin Alaya	
Judgment	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI
On a 'scale of journals', what 'quality of journal' <i>should</i> this be published in?	4.5	(3.0, 5.0)
What 'quality journal' do you expect this work <i>will</i> be published in?	2.0	(0.0, 4.0)
See here for more details on these tiers.	<p><i>We summarize these as:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.0: Marginally respectable/Little to no value • 1.0: OK/Somewhat valuable • 2.0: Marginal B-journal/Decent field journal • 3.0: Top B-journal/Strong field journal • 4.0: Marginal A-Journal/Top field journal • 5.0: A-journal/Top journal 	

Evaluation management discussion, process, considerations, synthesis

(This section was written by David Reinstein, joint evaluation manager for this paper.)

Why we prioritized this paper, how we considered it

“Should people concerned about catastrophic and existential (bio)risk support increases in funding for science?” – this seems to be the most explicit attempt to assess and quantify this important question. It seems to be influencing Open Philanthropy, which continues to fund hundreds of millions of dollars in science and technology research.¹⁷

From The Unjournal’s prioritization assessor:

This report develops a quantitative model of the returns of bioscience [and biotech] in the presence of catastrophic risks. The modelling is based on estimates from superforecasters and domain experts in Tetlock's Existential Risk Persuasion Tournament and integrates various existential risk concepts (e.g. time of perils). ...

The overall conclusion of the report ... may reassure [Effective Altruists] ... who advocate for slowing down bioscience research to mitigate GCBRs, and influence the investments such EAs make in biorisk reduction.

Conflict of Interest concerns

The author of this paper, Matt Clancy, is head of Open Philanthropy's Innovation Policy Program (IPP). As noted, Open Philanthropy is a major funder in the space of meta-science research, and impact-driven research in general. Open Philanthropy is also the largest funder of organizations and researchers in the Effective Altruism movement. The Unjournal has connections to this movement and has received funding from EA and EA-adjacent organizations, including organizations funded by Open Philanthropy. We're considering directly seeking funding from Open Philanthropy in the future. Similar concerns may apply to the evaluators, who may consider applying for Open Philanthropy in the future, may work at organizations connected to Open Philanthropy, etc.

Nonetheless, I believe this presents only a small conflict of interest in this case. In my general experience and in this particular case, the author and Open Philanthropy have shown a desire for truth-seeking and a willingness to receive constructive criticism and to respond to it in good faith. I hope this is self-evident here, but the reader should judge for themselves.

Overall conclusions and interpretation

The paper's main claims are the following.

Claim 1. A marginal increase in (bio)science funding is robustly a good thing, under most reasonable assumptions, if we ignore existential and civilizational risks.

At least from the author's and Open Philanthropy's points of view, this is probably seen mainly an *instrumental* claim. Open Philanthropy is deeply concerned about human extinction or civilizational collapse, and the author (Matt Clancy) does not make any arguments for ignoring these risks.

Claim 2. If we consider these '(bio) x-risks' the above conclusion ~depends on whether we believe the more optimistic superforecasters' predictions for these risks, or the more pessimistic domain-experts' predictions

The domain expert forecasts are high enough, for example, that if we think the future is "worth" more than 100 years of current social welfare, in one version of my model we would not want to accelerate science, because the health and income benefits would be outweighed by the increases in the remote but extremely bad possibility that new technology leads to the end of human civilization. However, if we

accept the much lower forecasts of extinction risks from the superforecasters, then we would need to put very very high values on the long-run future

(Weakly held) Claim 3: We should believe the superforecaster risk estimates more than the domain experts

Implication (Perhaps weakly claimed): A marginal increase in (bio)science funding is likely to be good for welfare, in expectation

Key issues, suggestions for evaluators

From our own reading, and after consulting with the author, we found a few issues that seemed particularly important to consider (possible sensitivities and cruxes). We sourced three evaluators, asking each to consider focusing on issues relevant to their own expertise, and sharing [these “managers’ notes” with them](#). In particular, we asked

1. Mike Hinge to check the models’ calculations and code,
2. Yassin Alaya to consider the parameter choices, especially the choice of discount rates, and
3. Gregory J. Lewis to focus on the characterization and measurement of the assessed bio-risks.

They were all also asked to consider the methodology, the policy implications, the characterization of the results, etc.¹⁸

Calculations, code, transparency

Mike Hinge seems to have checked both the Python code and the Google Sheet calculations carefully. He finds only a “single discrepancy [in the code] that doesn’t significantly change the results” and “could not find any calculation errors” in the sheet. This is comforting: there are signs that even papers published in economics journals may have meaningful computational errors.¹⁹

Hinge also suggests “a small amount of work to clean [the spreadsheet] up and add some functionality could make it a useful tool ... For example, a simple table of contents, key assumptions on one sheet that all others link to, as well as the ability to run and compare scenarios to see sensitivities (such as the impact of varying the discount factor or peril dynamics) would go a long way in raising its usability.” Given the high value of this question, and the apparent strength of the research, I agree that this would be worth a modest investment. However, while Google Sheets may be the most universally familiar collaborative tool, I suspect more structured code+dashboarding tools would be even more useful (Squiggle notebooks, Quarto, Shiny, etc.)

Epistemic discount rates and other parameters

Evaluator 2 focused on the choice of parameters, especially the “epistemic discount rates”. The author responded carefully, both offering further justification and explaining and showing how results vary with

parameters (see the given table). This was helpful.

I agree with evaluator 2, who (in a followup comment) asked the author to extend AR Table 1 to consider the sensitivity in the model *with* existential risk. They asked "Does the conclusion that a lower discount rate favours science also hold in the model with existential risk?"

In future, perhaps an interactive dashboard (where the user can adjust the parameters) would also be useful for readers, both to get a sense of how the model works, and to (I believe the hosted Google Sheet goes in this direction).

The author agrees there is some room for more in-depth modeling, particularly in considering excess mortality in the time of perils.²⁰

Non-Bio risks

As the author notes "all three reviewers noted at various points [...] that this analysis should be extended to include AI risk". Evaluators 2 and 3 "Note that the paper stacks the deck against concluding in favor of a science slowdown by comparing all the benefits of science to only a subset of the risks of science, namely the risks emerging from biotechnology" (quote from author's response).

Clancy acknowledges that "the report should have spent more time on this question" of why it is reasonable to ignore the impact of funding science on other risk areas in considering the paper's main question. Thankfully, he responds in detail.

He first considers catastrophic risks that might be affected by science *other than* ~pathogens or artificial intelligence (AI). He tentatively argues that the impact of science on most of these is either negligible or favorable (e.g., nuclear weapons and fossil fuel technology have *already* been developed, and future research may mitigate these risks). Here I think he is too optimistic. I suspect there are other unknown ways in which scientific progress could lead to new and dangerous weapons and other risks, e.g., autonomous drones or risk categories we may be little aware of ("risk x"). Evaluator 2 (Alaya) echoed the same concern.

Focusing on AI, Clancy offers three approaches to modeling the returns to science...²¹

Co-evaluation Manager's summary (Joel Christoph's comments)

This section synthesizes the evaluators' comments, the author's responses, and my own assessment of key issues in the paper.

1. Forecast Weighting: Superforecasters vs. Domain Experts

The evaluators noted that the report relies heavily on superforecaster estimates of existential risk, while domain experts provide significantly higher projections (20x for mortality risk, 140x for extinction risk). The author acknowledged this discrepancy and explained that superforecasters' track record in probabilistic reasoning makes them a useful reference point.

My assessment: While the author presents a reasonable justification for favoring superforecasters, the divergence in estimates is substantial. A more systematic approach—such as Bayesian updating or scenario-weighted modeling—would improve transparency and robustness. If Open Philanthropy's decision-making leans on these forecasts, it would be useful to test how sensitive conclusions are to alternative weighting schemes.

2. Sensitivity Analysis on Key Parameters

Evaluators questioned whether the model sufficiently accounts for alternative discount rates, time horizon assumptions for biotech threats, and how existential risk interacts with economic growth. The author responded by expanding Table 1 and providing additional rationale for the chosen discount rates.

My assessment: The added analysis is helpful, but the sensitivity testing could go further. It would be valuable to explicitly show how different epistemic discount rates affect the core conclusions, particularly when existential risks are considered. Extending the model's time horizon to stress-test these assumptions would also be informative.

3. AI as a Factor in Risk Mitigation

Some evaluators pointed out that the report models biotech risks in isolation, assuming offensive capabilities (e.g., synthetic biology threats) could outpace defense. However, AI-driven biosecurity tools could significantly alter this dynamic. The author provided an extensive response on modeling AI risks and even incorporated a toy model to examine AI's potential role.

My assessment: The author's response is substantive and acknowledges that AI could be both a stabilizing and destabilizing force. However, the toy model is a first step, and further development of AI risk projections—perhaps integrating them into the main framework—could strengthen the overall analysis. The core question remains: if AI significantly reduces biorisk, how does this impact the calculus on science acceleration?

4. Model Transparency and Usability

Evaluators found the quantitative model well-structured but suggested that key assumptions and parameters should be easier to adjust and test. The author agreed and mentioned plans to refine the spreadsheet and Python model but did not commit to any major structural changes.

My assessment: A more user-friendly, interactive tool—such as a streamlined dashboard where users can toggle key parameters—would greatly improve the model’s accessibility. While Google Sheets is a convenient option, something like a Squiggle notebook or Quarto dashboard might be a more effective long-term solution.

5. AI vs. Biotech as the Dominant Risk Factor

Some evaluators questioned whether AI-driven risks might be more relevant than biotech risks in shaping the “Time of Perils.” The author acknowledged this concern and engaged with it by modeling AI risk scenarios, noting that AI could dramatically alter the trajectory of both existential risk and scientific progress.

My assessment: The author’s response is thorough and provides an initial modeling attempt, and highlights areas where future work could expand the analysis. While biotech remains a well-defined risk area, incorporating AI timelines into the main risk model would provide a clearer picture of how these risks interact. This would be particularly valuable for policymakers who must allocate resources between different risk areas.

Conclusion

The evaluators provided thoughtful critiques, and the author has responded meaningfully in most cases. My revised assessment clarifies that the author did engage extensively with AI concerns and does not argue that biotech risks are necessarily the most immediate concern. However, some areas—particularly forecast weighting, sensitivity analysis, and further refinement of AI risk modeling—could still benefit from additional work. Addressing these would strengthen the report’s robustness and policy relevance.

References

1. Clancy, M. (2024). The Returns to Science in the Presence of Technological Risk. arXiv preprint. <http://arxiv.org/pdf/2312.14289>

Footnotes

1. We asked them to rank this paper “heuristically” as a percentile “relative to all serious research in the same area that you have encountered in the last three years.” We requested they “consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice. ↵
2. See ranking tiers discussed [here](#). ↵
3. Note: if you are reading this before, or soon after this has been publicly released, the ratings from this paper may not yet have been incorporated into that data presentation. ↵
- 4.

Judge the quality of the research heuristically. Consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice.

↵

5. "Do the authors do a good job of (i) stating their main questions and claims, (ii) providing strong evidence and powerful approaches to inform these, and (iii) correctly characterizing the nature of their evidence?"

This was on the newer form only ↵

6.

To what extent does the project contribute to the field or to practice, particularly in ways that are directly or indirectly relevant to global priorities and impactful interventions?

↵

7. Are methods clearly justified and explained? Are methods and their underlying assumptions reasonable? Are the results likely to be robust to changes in the assumptions? Have the authors avoided bias and questionable research practices? ↵

8. Methods clear and (conditional on underlying assumptions) reasonable and appropriate. Again my worry is the findings are predicated on inappropriate assumptions. ↵

9. Are concepts clearly defined? Is the reasoning transparent? Are conclusions consistent with the evidence (or formal proofs) presented? Are the data and/or analysis, including tables and figures, relevant to the argument? ↵

10. Generally clearly written and transparently reasoned. Use of benchmarking, breakevens etc. particularly helpful. ↵

11.

Would another researcher be able to replicate the analysis? Are the method and its details explained sufficiently? Is the source of the data clear? Is the data made as widely available as possible, with clear labeling and explanation? Do the authors provide resources that are likely to enable future research and meta-analysis?

↵

12.

Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic and relevant to practitioners?

↵

13.

The latter ratings were merged in the newer form

"Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions?"

"Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic? Do the authors report results that are relevant to practitioners? Do they provide useful quantified estimates (costs, benefits, etc.)?" ↵

14. Again, a lot of the lower tail is owed to >10% credence from me on "this could be substantially misleading". ↵

15. Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions? ↵

16.

The latter ratings were merged in the newer form

"Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions?"

"Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic? Do the authors report results that are relevant to practitioners? Do they provide useful quantified estimates (costs, benefits, etc.)?" ↵

17. But this began as an *internal* report; Matt Clancy is head of Open Philanthropy's Innovation Policy Program (IPP). So, some external scrutiny could be helpful. ↵

18. We gave some further specific suggestions, e.g., to consider the forecast weighting, an extension to AI risks, and the modeling of technical diffusion; see [the "managers' notes"](#). ↵

19. Brodeur et al (2024) find "a high rate of fully computationally reproducible results (over 85%)" ... "The remaining 15% included studies with partial availability of analytic code and data or cases where some codes failed to run or produced inconsistent results". But most of the articles in their sample were already computationally reproduced by data editors. They cite earlier papers (Chang and Li (2022); Gertler et al.

(2018); Wood et al. (2018)) that suggest the potential for higher rates of important computational errors in other journals. ↵

20. Note from co-evaluation manager (David Reinstein). I do not yet understand the model well enough to comment on the parameter justification and interpretation – I hope to add more here in a future update of this summary, after some more careful reading and discussion. ↵

21. David Reinstein note: I hope to continue this discussion when I have a chance, adapting my existing notes, and following this up with a discussion of the 'Superforecasters vs. Evaluators' issue.

↵

References

1.

<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2312.14289>

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